

An Overview, Introduction and Curated list of MLOps Tools

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ABSTRACT

The set of engineering practices adopted by the data science and engineering teams to manage the entire machine learning life cycle using MLOps (Machine Learning Operations). The ultimate objective of all industrial Machine Learning initiatives is to create Machine Learning products and swiftly implement them in production. However, many Machine Learning initiatives fall short of promises since it is very difficult to automate and operationalize Machine Learning products. This problem is addressed by the MLOps Paradigm. To work with the MLOps the individual has to be aware of variety the tools used to help in different phases of life cycle. This article has created an expert knowledge about the MLOps tools used throughout Machine Learning life cycle in addition to that a comprehensive knowledge about the introduction and its operations.

Keywords: MLOps, tools

INTRODUCTION

The term MLOps is combination of ML and DevOps, according to the person who coined the phrase. The entire machine learning life cycle, from development to deployment and monitoring, is managed by MLOps (Machine Learning Operations) using a variety of tools and frameworks. These tools can be given as a complete, end-to-end platforms or grouped according to their functions. This paper will discuss these wide range and variety of tools in detail.

The MLOps is evolving rapidly, MLOps= people +process +technology with a goal of reliability, reproducibility and scalability and introduces the data dependency, model decay and retraining. The reason of necessity of it is ML models fail in production without operational discipline. Training, concept drift and data drift can also be managed; manual ML workflows don't scale and the production ML needs the monitoring and retraining pipelines. The key concepts of future of MLOps [19] are Integration with AutoML, increased focus on Responsible AI, Standardization of MLOps tools and Platforms and stronger Governance and regulatory requirements.

Developing the model is essentially the primary responsibility of the data scientist. It is the responsibility of the MLOps environment where the deployment and updating with the production level reliability. It entails

- a) making platform-related decisions, such as
 - How to deploy and trigger models.
 - How will we provide the model with real-time data?
 - How will we monitor the performance of the model?

- Where will model development take place?
- b) Setting up, configuring and providing support for any platforms that can be selected.
- c) Additionally, guide the data scientists
 - How to utilize, implement, and build for the platform(s) we have chosen.
 - Sometimes the data scientist simply gives a trained model object, and we are responsible for setting up and deploying a container.

The three complementary operational practices DataOps, AIOps and MLOps designed in order to handle the complexity of contemporary data-driven and AI-driven systems. They each concentrate on a distinct phase of the data-to-AI lifecycle, although having similar concepts like automation and monitoring. DataOps is a collection of techniques that enhances data analytics pipelines dependability, quality and speed having a goal of trusted delivery, high-quality data quickly for downstream AI/ML systems and analytics. AI for IT Operations (AIOps), uses analytics and ML to automate and enhance IT Operations with the aim of improving system performance, availability and dependability using AI-driven insights [4]. The successful AI-driven enterprise requires DataOps for data reliability, MLOps for ML life cycle management, and AIOps for intelligent IT operations, all working together to support scalable and trust worthy AI systems. The recent improvements in technology considerably facilitate MLOps. Specially, the incorporation of AI into different ML platforms and tools has already had impact and will continue to do so. Wastson et. al explains the currently available AI capabilities to assist MLOps [13].

The best MLOp's technologies for data and pipeline versioning, model deployment and serving, workflow orchestration, experiment tracking, model metadata management, and model monitoring in production [9], [11], [12]. The finest MLOp's tools for model building, deployment and monitoring are described in the below sections of the paper.

The role of MLOps engineer is to deploy ML models in cloud infrastructure like AWS, Azure, GCP, IBM using tools [2] like MLflow and Azure data Factory to ensure that all of the AI models developed in software applications are scalable and maintainable and having a proficiency in writing scripts using python is prerequisite and essential for this field. A basic understanding of Linux will also be beneficial, as will familiarity with cloud platforms, version control systems like GIT, ML and tools like MLFlow.

The curated list among them of above MLOps Tools with respect to development lifecycle phases are

ML life cycle phase	Tools
Data Engineering/ETL and Pipelines	Apache Spark, dbt, Talend, Apache Airflow, Apache Beam, Airbyte.
Data Storage	Hadoop HDFS, Amazon S3, google Cloud Storage, Azure Blob storage, Snowflake, BigQuery, Postgre SQL/ MySQL
Data Ingestion Tools	Apache Kafka, Apache NiFi, Logstash, Flume, AWS Kinesis, Google Pub/Sub

Development and Experimentation	Jupyter Notebook/ Jupyter Lab, Google Colab, VSCode, PyCharm, Kaggle Notebooks
ML/DL frameworks	Keras, PyTorch, TensorFlow, Scikit-learn, MXNet, JAX
Experiment Tracking	MLflow, Neptune.ai, Weights & Biases
Feature Stores	Hopsworks Feature Store, Feast
Model Serving (Deployment)	BentoML, Triton Inference Server, ONNX Runtime, TorchServe, Tensorflow Serving
Data and Model Versioning	Git/GitHub, DVC (Data Version Control)
Containerization & Environment Management	Docker, Kubernetes, Conda, Podman, Singularity
API Frameworks for ML Deployment	FastAPI, Flask, gRPC, Django
Workflow Pipeline and Orchestration	Kubeflow Pipelines, Argo Workflows, Mage AI, Dagster, Perfect, ZenML, Flyte, Kedro Pipelines
Hyperparameter Optimization	Hyperopt, SigOpt, Google Vizier, Optuna, Talos, Scikit-Optimize
Cloud MLOps/End to End Platforms	AWS SageMaker, Microsoft Azure Machine Learning, Databricks, GCP Vertex AI, IBM Watson Studio, H2O.ai, Cloudera, Iguazio, Valohai, AliBaba Cloud ML, DataRobot, MetaFlow, DagsHub
CI/CD Tools	GitHub Actions, Jenkins, GitLab CI/CD, Azure DevOps, Bitbucket Pipelines
Model Monitoring	Evidently AI, Arize AI, Prometheus and Grafana, Elastic Stack (ELK), Fiddler AI
Model Registry	MLflow Model Registry, SageMaker Model Registry, Azure ML Registry, Neptune Model Registry
LLM Frameworks	Qdrant, LangChain
Dataset Labeling & Annotation	Scale AI, Labelbox, Kili, Super Annotate, Encord Annotate, Snorkel Flow, Amazon Ground Truth
Model Observability	Unravel Data, Fiddler AI, Losswise, Superwise, MLrun, WhyLabs, Aporia, Deep Checks
Model Testing	Deepchecks ML Models Testing, TruEra
Runtime Engines	Ray, Nuclio

Table 1: MLOps tools with LifeCycle

The authors named as Nipuni Hewage and Dulani Meedeniya explained clearly about the MLOps tool stack. The comparison of features with the tools which helps when deciding which platform is best for the environment used for developing solutions. Basically, the good knowledge with respect to tools has support the development process and made easy and also the required efforts will be estimate [7]. The Automated ML named as AutoML in combination with MLOps could work has been clearly explained by discussing about the maturity levels of various Multinational organizations such as Google and Microsoft proposed by Georgios Symeonidis et al. How to choose the right tools by discussing

preprocessing, Modeling, operationalization tools, AutoML tools and platforms. The AutoML is the paradigm shift in maturity and efficiency seek [15].

Many ML initiatives fall short of expectations because it is very difficult to automate and operationalize ML products. This difficulty of problem is addressed by MLOps paradigm. MLOps encompasses a number of elements, including development culture, sets of concepts and best practices. MLOps is still a nebulous word, though and its implications for professionals and researchers are unclear. The Dominik et al [1] conducted a survey of mixed-method research, tool and expert interviews review. It provides an aggregated overview of the necessary components, roles, architecture, workflows and principles. Discusses an excellent survey of list of software industries with its size having an experience of engineers in ML and DevOps working with them.

The Jasper Stone et al; avoids the confusion regarding using standard MLOps lifecycle and maturity models by incorporating the LLMOps [16]. Adrian et al write a systematic literature review of papers with reference to the classes, tools and process steps of MLOps by performing the research Query on the databases like ScienceDirect, IEEE, Proquest, Springer, EBSCO [3], [14].

Raj et al. presented a frame work for scalable fleet-analytic techniques (ML in distributed systems) in [20], [21], enabling ML-Ops methodologies with an emphasis on IOT edge devices. By using the models on the specialized edge devices, the suggested scalable architecture was used and assessed for robustness and efficiency in experiments including air quality prediction in different campus rooms. Continuous integration, continuous delivery, and continuous deployment are all made possible by CI/CD automation. It completes the steps of build, test, deliver and deploy. It increases overall productivity by giving developers quick feedback on the success or failure of specific processes. DevOps concepts are implemented using CI/CD. Thus, it might be considered a DevOps Strategy. The CI/CD practices are [17], [23] clearly explained with implementation by Gourav shah [24]. Gourav provides a practical transition from DevOps to MLOps and emphasizes on automation, collaboration, scalability, reproducibility to build and maintain reliable production grade ML systems by using Docker, Kubernetes, Python, Git and Cloud platforms.

Habeeb Agoro, Henry Lawson explains the Benefits of integration of MLOps with data engineering [18] are Streamlines Data pipelines (reduced latency, scalability, consistent data flow, real time processing, automation), improved data quality and consistency (factors are automated data validation, data cleaning processes, version control, consistent data formats, enhanced monitoring), accelerated model development and deployment cycle, enhanced collaboration between data engineers and data scientists

Various applications like agronomy, healthcare, retail and many more, are explained using case studies by Shashi and et al. [8], [10], [18]. The value of maintaining a robust monitoring and feedback mechanism is the essential findings from the observations of these case studies. The issues regarding performance degradation, ML model drift and facilitating timely interventions are identified in the continuous monitoring. Another important observation is the need for effective versioning, configuration management, collaboration between operation teams and data engineers, reproducibility, adaption and

consistency. These are the challenges have need to be faced as the MLOps engineer or developer. In addition to these challenges there are some problems while designing the system using MLOps discussed in the below section. The reason of most likely have been using the MLOps practices in now days are the assets of using these MLOps practices is much more than the predicaments.

Metrics for Monitoring and Deployment of ML systems

The various metrics available for ML system monitoring [22] are

Model's Performance

This metric aids in assessing whether a model is adequate by analyzing task-specific statistics. For classification problems, key metrics include recall, precision, false positive rate (FPR), True positive rate (TPR), and confusion matrix. Despite potential lag between output and true labels, key indicators of model performance are accuracy, comparative gains, and the credibility of predictions.

Output Distribution

Model degradation is shown by the distribution shift of the expected outputs between data from the training and production phases. Metrics like the Divergence Index or the Population Stability Index may be useful in warning such changes. The statistic is crucial for assessing the reliability of current models on the new data, particularly in time-series-based datasets.

Concept Drift

It refers to the degradation of model performance due to outdated patterns that the model has learned. This issue highlights the importance of detecting active and passive concept drift, particularly in distributed environments.

Bias/Fairness

The trained model may exhibit bias towards a particular class or group, which can be assessed through the measurement of accuracy difference (AD) for each class. Additionally, evaluating the model on specific data slices can provide a detailed analysis of its performance.

Feature importance change

The model's performance may remain stable; however, change in feature importance could signal prediction drift, suggesting the need for new data collection for retraining.

Numerical stability

Numeric errors may occur during the model training, leading to incorrect predictions in production without explicit errors. Ensuring numerical stability is critical for maintaining robustness.

Metrics for system monitoring for deployment infrastructure related errors are

Throughput

Average predictions returned in one second indicate high throughput, reflecting a healthy system. However, throughput measurements may be influenced by additional metrics such as total hits per week, average hit size, and error rate.

Latency

Low latency is essential for a positive user experience, as it measures response time. Effective metrics should include responses from all tiers, considering both the average time to answer requests and other factors like perceived page load time.

Disk utilization

Monitoring free disk space is crucial to prevent data loss and server downtime. Additionally, file system statistics can aid in assessing the health status of applications.

System's Uptime

System uptime is a key reliability measure that indicates service availability, making it particularly valuable for web-based applications.

Number of API calls

Monitoring API calls can effectively gauge maximum load and system availability when serving a model to multiple users.

CPU/GPU Usage

Monitoring CPU and GPU usage is essential for identifying inputs that lead to longer computation times, which aids in model tuning for improved user experience. Adjusting the infrastructure's capacity and configuration may involve resizing resources to meet the necessary serving capabilities.

Problems in Designing the ML systems

Machine Learning is a very helpful way to quickly build systems that make complex predictions. The easy wins don't have a cost is dangerous. It is enjoyable to build ML but ML shipping is challenging [25]. When we look at machine learning systems in the real world, they often have huge ongoing maintenance costs. This can be clearly understood using the software engineering concept of technical debt. There are some risks need to take into account when designing a system include entanglement, boundary erosion, hidden feedback loops, data dependencies, configuration issues, changes in the outside world, the presence of uncleared consumers and many different system-level anti-patterns. One crucial realization is that technological debt is a problem that both researchers and engineers must be conscious of. It is rarely a good idea to pursue research solutions that offer a small improvement in accuracy at the expense of significant increase in systems complexity. Progress can be slowed down even by the addition of one or two seemingly harmless data dependencies. A change in team culture is frequently the only way to make the kind of commitment needed to pay off ML related technical debt. The long-term viability of successful ML teams depends on acknowledging, recognizing and prioritizing this effort [5]. The problem

of Glue code, Data drift, configuration debt, Pipeline jungles, Feedback loops solutions are given as Modular pipeline, continuous monitoring, Model registries, Orchestration tools, Governance & Audits respectively.

The Iranian software developers give a brief overview of the developing field of MLOps and its importance in resolving the difficulties business encounter in efficiently managing machine learning models has been provided [6]. The results show that among the main issues practitioners confront are issues with data quality, a lack of resources and obstacles with model deployment. One of the most important challenges in successfully deploying MLOps is a collaboration across the ML, DevOps, Ops and science teams.

A vast array of tools and platforms were available in the MLOps landscape with the goal of assisting business and people in effectively managing components or the full machine learning lifecycle. The field is developing quickly, giving practitioners a wide range of choices for successfully implementing ML. The most significant MLOps tools and platforms used by top IT business worldwide are presented in this section, along with some of their proprietary MLOps infrastructure. From data preparation and model building to deployment and monitoring, end-to-end MLOps system provide a unified ecosystem that improves the whole ML workflow.

Conclusion

The tools used in a variety of industries have been successfully applied on case studies from the real world demonstrate how MLOps techniques revolutionary effects on the model performance and operational efficiency. To sum up, MLOps has become an essential field for business looking to successfully utilize ML, MLOps promotes team work, boosts output and guarantees the dependable deployment and upkeep of models by fusing DevOps best practices with specific approaches for managing ML process.

Future work

Initially from the past decade the no sufficient papers are available in the field of MLOps and not explored much but it has been gaining the improvement of work and research has been done under this field widely, but model monitoring steps are not yet to be clearly defined according to market standards in the model production process of MLOps. This paper does the general literature survey of few papers but in the future, plan to conduct a more research on the literature survey and when significant changes in the wide variety of tools at current and future introductions are done.

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